

1 **Genes that influence HIV-1 latency.**

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6 Genes described to influence latency included Xpb, Paf1c, and Ccnt1. HDAC inhibitors have described
7 latency reversal potential. We measured total transcription in cells treated with HDAC inhibitors SAHA or
8 Romidepsin to understand molecular mechanisms underlying latency reversal involving HDACi. Cells
9 treated with HDACi experienced an imprinting switch marked by activation of *PEG10*. HDACi with SAHA
10 or Romidepsin resulted in silencing of *Brpf3*, *Echdc2*, and *Gtf2ird2b*. A gene product encoded by
11 *Cttnbp2nl* was activated during latency reversal associated with chemical HDACi.

12 Citations

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